

Certificate of Calibration

THERMOMETER
19205E

This certificate is issued in accordance with the laboratory accreditation requirements of the United Kingdom Accreditation Service. It provides traceability of measurement to the SI system of units and/or to units of measurement realised at the National Physical Laboratory or other recognised national metrology institutes. This certificate may not be reproduced other than in full, except with the prior written approval of the issuing laboratory.

FOR: Facility for Airborne Atmospheric Measurements
Building 146
Cranfield University
Cranfield
Bedfordshire
MK43 0AL

For the attention of Dr Hannah Price

DESCRIPTION: Thermistor constructed by FAAM using a Rosemount Engineering housing connected to a customer supplied Data Logging Unit (DLU)

IDENTIFICATION: Type: E102AL, Serial No. 19205E

**PREVIOUS
CERTIFICATE:** 2014070095 dated 4 March 2015

**DATES OF
CALIBRATION:** 24 September to 3 October 2018

Reference: 2018080037-4

Date of issue: 30 October 2018

Checked by:

Signed:

Name: Mr P A Carroll

Page 1 of 4

(Authorised Signatory)

on behalf of NPLML

This certificate is consistent with the capabilities that are included in Appendix C of the MRA drawn up by the CIPM. Under the MRA, all participating institutes recognise the validity of each other's calibration and measurement certificates for the quantities, ranges and measurement uncertainties specified in Appendix C (for details see <http://www.bipm.org>).

NATIONAL PHYSICAL LABORATORY

Continuation Sheet

MEASUREMENTS

The thermometer was calibrated in a test chamber, in air, by comparison against reference platinum resistance thermometers (PRTs). Traceability of measurement was provided by calibration of these thermometers to the International Temperature Scale of 1990 (ITS-90) through NPL Temperature Standards.

As requested the thermistor was connected to a data logging unit (DLU) provided by the customer via an Amphenol and then a D-type connector. The DLU was programmed by the customer to switch every 60 minutes between an excitation voltage of nominally 5 volts and $5/\sqrt{2}$ volts. The excitation voltage (V_{ref}) and the De-iced (DI) and Non De-iced (NDI) voltages were measured using an Agilent 34970A data acquisition unit with traceability to National Standards. A set of 10 readings were taken from the instrument under test at each excitation voltage with a data logging interval of 1 minute. At each temperature a time of not less than 3 hours was allowed for temperature to equilibrate.

Before and after the calibration voltages from the DLU were recorded without a thermistor connected to the De-iced socket. These results appear in Table 1 below.

The value of the applied condition is shown in the first column of Table 2 below. The values measured from the instrument under test are quoted with their expanded uncertainties. This quoted uncertainty relates to the period of the calibration and is not an indication of the long-term stability of the instrument.

The ambient conditions in the NPL humidity laboratory were $23\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 3\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and less than 80 % relative humidity.

Table 1 - DLU Values Without a Thermistor Connected to the De-iced Socket

	Test Measurements		
	Logged V_{ref} Voltage	Logged DI Voltage	Logged NDI Voltage
	V	V	V
Before Calibration	3.537	0.003	2.649
Before Calibration	5.001	0.003	3.745
After Calibration	3.537	0.003	2.648
After Calibration	5.001	0.003	3.745

Reference: 2018080037-4

Checked by:

Page 2 of 4

NATIONAL PHYSICAL LABORATORY

Continuation Sheet

Table 2 - Calibration Results

Applied Condition Measured Temperature	Test Measurements			
	Logged Vref Voltage	Logged DI Voltage	Logged NDI Voltage	Expanded Uncertainty of the Voltage Output
°C	V	V	V	°C
-60.17 #	3.537	2.449	2.648	±0.14
-60.16 #	5.001	3.462	3.745	±0.14
-50.09 #	3.537	2.284	2.649	±0.10
-50.09 #	5.001	3.228	3.745	±0.10
-40.10	3.537	2.041	2.649	±0.08
-40.09	5.001	2.881	3.745	±0.08
-30.02	3.537	1.725	2.649	±0.08
-29.96	5.001	2.429	3.745	±0.08
-19.90	3.537	1.373	2.648	±0.07
-19.90	5.001	1.933	3.745	±0.07
-9.87	3.537	1.039	2.649	±0.06
-9.85	5.001	1.462	3.745	±0.06
+0.12	3.537	0.757	2.649	±0.04
+0.14	5.001	1.065	3.745	±0.04
+10.12	3.537	0.539	2.648	±0.04
+10.11	5.001	0.760	3.745	±0.04
+20.19	3.537	0.379	2.649	±0.04
+20.20	5.001	0.534	3.745	±0.04
+30.15	3.537	0.267	2.648	±0.04
+30.16	5.001	0.377	3.745	±0.04
+40.11	3.537	0.189	2.648	±0.04
+40.14	5.001	0.267	3.745	±0.04
+50.09	3.537	0.136	2.648	±0.04
+50.08	5.001	0.192	3.745	±0.04

NOTE: # Points below -40 °C are outside the range of NPL's UKAS accreditation for air temperature

Reference: 2018080037-4

Checked by:

UNCERTAINTIES

The standard uncertainty of the applied condition represents a combination of the uncertainties arising from calibration and estimated stability of the reference standards, and from the method of transfer to the instrument under test.

The standard uncertainty of measurement is calculated by combining the uncertainty of the applied condition, the resolution of the instrument and its standard deviation for the period of the test. An uncertainty contribution has been included for rounding to give results an equivalent resolution of 0.01 °C.

The reported expanded uncertainty is based on a standard uncertainty multiplied by a coverage factor $k = 2$, providing a coverage probability of approximately 95 %. The uncertainty evaluation has been carried out in accordance with UKAS requirements.

Reference: 2018080037-4

Checked by:

Page 4 of 4